

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa)

Stop series in Asia and Africa: A geolinguistic approach to linguistic patterns

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Abstract: In accordance with the overview provided in Chapter XIII “Stop series” of the *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa II*, this article presents individual linguistic maps for each feature on the stop series (denti-alveolar sounds), thereby offering further support for the preceding descriptions.*

Keywords: *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa*; consonant system; stop series; denti-alveolar; geographical distribution

1. Introduction

This article provides a more detailed account of the material presented in Suzuki (2022), which is the overview prepared for Chapter XIII of *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa II* (LAAA-2; Suzuki et al. 2023). It also incorporates the entire data set on individual maps for each topic addressed in the chapter, thereby, offering a comprehensive visual representation of the information.

In contrast to the other contributions on the present featured theme, including sibling terms (Fukushima 2024), alignment (Shirai 2024), and numeral systems (Fukazawa 2024), the cross-linguistic overview of the stop series topic is challenging due to the need to summarise the data based on a common criterion; see Figure 1 for a reference. The series is represented by dental/denti-alveolar/alveolar (henceforth D/A) plosives and nasals. The project examined a system of D/A stop series that comprised the following components: /th-t-t’-d-dh-d’-nd-nt-nth-n-nh/ ([t^h-t-t’-d-d^h-d’-n^d-n^t-nth-n-n^h]) for

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a phonetic description). The symbols of each language group are distinguished by different colours, as shown in Table 1.

N.B. See Suzuki et al. (2023) for the detailed legend for each language group.

Fig. 1 The whole dataset of the stop series from LAAA-2.

Table 1 The language groups and colours

Language group	Color	Language group	Color
Ainu	Red	Korean	Light blue
Andamanese and language isolates (South Asia)	Black	Kra-Dai	Navy
Austroasiatic	Green	Kx'a (Kalahari Basin Area)	Light blue
Austronesian	Orange	Mongolic	Green
Caucasian	Light blue	Niger-Congo	Navy
Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Black	Nilo-Saharan	Green
Dravidian	Red	Semitic	Brown
Hmong-Mien	Orange	Sinitic	Red
Indo-Aryan and Nuristani (South Asia)	Navy	Tibeto-Burman	Brown
Iranian	Orange	Tungusic	Orange
Japonic	Green	Turkic	Light blue
Khoe-Kwadi (Kalahari Basin Area)	Brown	Tuu (Kalahari Basin Area)	Orange
		Uralic	Light blue

The article deals with the following features: D/A series types, ejective, implosive, pharyngealisation, prenasalisation, voiceless nasal, glottalised stops, and the lack of D/A nasals. The D/A series types include several criteria.

2. D/A series types

Various D/A series types are attested in Asian and African languages. This section examines five types: /t/ only, non-nasal tripartite contrast /th-t-d/, non-nasal quadripartite contrast /th-t-d-dh/, voicing contrast, and aspiration contrasts. Although historical studies indicate that these types are mutually related, here, each description reflects its synchronic status in conjunction with its phonation and suprasegmental features (e.g., Zhu 2010 in Sinitic; Tournadre and Suzuki 2023 in Tibetic).

2.1. /t/ only (bipartite contrast /t-n/)

A two-way distinction represents the minimum D/A stop series system, in which the /t-n/ components are most widely attested in many languages, including Chukotko-Kamchatkan (Chukchi and Koryak), Ainu, Ōgami Ryukyuan of Japonic, Car Nicobarese of Austroasiatic, Austronesian, Khanty and Mansi of Uralic, Chuvash of Turkic, Dravidian, Cypriot Arabic, Pökoot of Nilo-Saharan, and Niger-Congo.

Other two-way distinction patterns are /th-t/ (a limited number of Sinitic varieties, Kra-Dai, Tujia of Tibeto-Burman) and /t-d/ (a limited number of Niger-Congo). As all these features are found in a vast geographical area spanning Asia and Africa, maps are not provided.

2.2. Non-nasal tripartite contrast

A non-nasal tripartite distinction /th-t-d/ is widely attested in several language groups, including Sinitic (particularly Wu varieties), Hmong-Mien, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasiatic, Austronesian, Indo-Aryan, Burushaski, Armenian, and Niger-Congo. Of these language groups, some varieties exhibit this distinction with prenasalised features, including /th-t-d-nd/ and /th-t-d-nd-nth/. Figures¹ 2 and 3 illustrate the language groups that demonstrate this non-nasal tripartite distinction. The distribution of these languages is concentrated in East and Southeast Asia.

Other tripartite contrasts comprising voicing, aspiration, prenasalisation, and glottalisation distinctions are also attested, albeit to a lesser extent. These include /t-d-nd/ (Japonic), /t-t²-d/ (Japonic), /th-t-t²/ (Korean), /th-d-dh/ (Sinitic), and /t-d-dh/ (Dravidian). As all of these are minority patterns, maps are not provided.

¹ For technical reasons, the tiny symbols may persist on the maps. However, their presence does not indicate the actual presence of the corresponding feature.

Fig. 2 Distribution of the tripartite contrast /th-t-d/.

Fig. 3 Distribution of the tripartite contrast /th-t-d/ in Asia.

2.3. Non-nasal quadripartite contrast

A non-nasal quadripartite distinction, /th-t-d-dh/, is attested in several South Asian and Himalayan languages, including Tibeto-Burman, Indo-Aryan, Dravidian, and Iranian. As indicated in the descriptions of the Tibeto-Burman and Dravidian language groups, this series is attributed to Indo-Aryan language contact. The quadripartite distinction is observed in a limited number of major language groups, namely Indo-Aryan and Dravidian. A small number of varieties within the following language groups exhibit the quadripartite distinction: Sinitic, Hmong-Mien, Austroasiatic from eastern Asia and Kx'a (excluding the click series) from southern Africa. Figure 4 illustrates the language groups that exhibit a non-nasal quadripartite distinction.

Fig. 4 Distribution of the quadripartite contrast /th-t-d-dh/.

2.4. Voicing contrast

A contrast between voiceless and voiced plosives (i.e., /t-d/) is attested in many language families, including Japonic, Sinitic, Hmong-Mien, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasiatic, Austronesian, Tungusic, Uralic, Mongolic, Turkic, Indo-Aryan, Burushaski, Dravidian, Iranian, Armenian, Nilo-Saharan, Niger-Congo, Tu, Kx'a, and Khoe-Kwadi. The data indicates that a majority of these languages exhibit a voicing contrast; hence, Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the language groups **without this contrast**.

It is noteworthy that Liang et al. (2023) address the causal chain relationships between climate, voice quality, and tone in languages in China. The data from Asia and Africa indicate that voicing distinction is a significant feature of languages from low latitudes.

Fig. 5 Distribution of the language groups without a voicing contrast.

Fig. 6 Distribution of the language groups without a voicing contrast in Asia.

2.5. Aspiration contrast

A contrast between voiceless aspirated and voiceless nonaspirated plosives (i.e., /th- t/) is attested in many language families, including Korean, Sinitic, Hmong-Mien, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasiatic, Austronesian, Mongolic, Turkic, Indo-Aryan, Burushaski, Dravidian, Iranian, Armenian, Nilo-Saharan, Niger-Congo, Tu, Kx'a and Khoe-Kwadi. Furthermore, some Saami languages (Uralic) also exhibit aspirated stops (Suzuki 2021). Figure 7 and 8 present the language groups with this contrast, while Figure 9 presents the language groups **without this contrast**.

Furthermore, an aspirated voiced plosive /dh/ (/d^h/) is documented in a number of language families, including Sinitic, Tibeto-Burman, Indo-Aryan, Dravidian, Iranian, Niger-Congo, Tuu, and Kx'a. No maps are provided for this feature.

Fig. 7 Distribution of the language groups with an aspiration contrast.

Fig. 8 Distribution of the language groups with an aspiration contrast in Asia.

Fig. 9 Distribution of the language groups without an aspiration contrast.

3. Ejective

The ejective sound is documented in a number of geographical locations, including the Caucasus, Ethiopia, easternmost Siberia, the Kalahari Basin Area, and southernmost Africa. It should be noted that the Korean /tʰ/ is not included in the list

of ejective sounds. For further details, refer to Kim and Duanmu (2004) and Duan and Zhu (2018). In Ethiopia, both Nilo-Saharan and Semitic languages exhibit the presence of an ejective. In the Caucasus region, the ejective plosive is a pervasive feature of a number of Caucasian languages, including Kartvelian, Abkhazo-Adyghean, and Nakho-Daghestanian, as well as the Ossetic (Iranian) languages spoken in that region. Figure 10 illustrates the language groups that possess an ejective phoneme, while Figures 11 and 12 present comprehensive maps of the Caucasus and the Red Sea-Ethiopia region, respectively.

Fig. 10 Distribution of the language groups with an ejective sound.

Fig. 11 Distribution of the language groups with an ejective sound in Caucasus.

Fig. 12 Distribution of the language groups with an ejective sound in Red Sea-Ethiopia area.

4. Implosive

Implosives are typically voiced; however, a voiceless counterpart has also been identified. The voiced implosive /d̥/ is attested in a number of language families, including Sinitic, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasiatic, Austronesian, Indo-Aryan, Semitic, Nilo-Saharan, and Niger-Congo. The voiceless implosive /t̥/ is attested exclusively in Niger-Congo as a phonemic status. In some cases, a contact-induced acquisition provides an appropriate explanation. Figure 13 illustrates the language groups that possess an implosive phoneme, while Figures 14 and 15 present detailed maps of East and Southeast Asia and Central Africa, respectively.

Fig. 13 Distribution of the language groups with an implosive sound.

Fig. 14 Distribution of the language groups with an implosive sound in East and Southeast Asia.

Fig. 15 Distribution of the language groups with an implosive sound in the central Africa.

5. Pharyngealisation

The occurrence of pharyngealised plosives has been documented in a number of languages, including Iranian, Semitic, Indo-Aryan spoken in Middle-East and Nilo-Saharan. The voiced type /dʕ/ is not attested in the majority of Nilo-Saharan languages. A systematic pharyngealised consonant feature, /tʕ-dʕ/, is predominantly attested in Semitic languages. Figure 16 illustrates the language groups that exhibit pharyngealised consonants, with the exception of Nilo-Saharan, for which the pharyngealised sounds were not distinguished in the original map of LAAA-2. Two languages from the Nilo-Saharan language family, Northern Songhay and Sudanese Berta, have been found to possess pharyngealised consonants. Figure 17 presents a detailed map of Middle East.

Fig. 16 Distribution of the language groups with pharyngealised consonants.

Fig. 17 Distribution of the language groups with pharyngealised consonants in Middle East.

Additionally, the pharyngealised feature is observed in Iranian languages to the west and Nilo-Saharan languages to the south, which are in turn connected to Semitic-speaking regions. The majority of Nilo-Saharan languages with pharyngealised features exhibit the phoneme /tʕ/, as do a number of Semitic and Iranian languages. As indicated in the descriptions of Semitic languages in LAAA-2, pharyngealisation is associated with ejective sounds (see Section 3), which are typically designated as ‘emphatic consonants’. These two features are distributed across a continuous geographical area, from the Caucasus to South Africa.

6. Prenasalisation

The occurrence of prenasalised plosives has been documented in several language families, including Japonic, Sinitic, Kra-Dai, Hmong-Mien, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasian, Austronesian, Nilo-Saharan, and Niger-Congo. While voiced prenasalised sounds are pervasive in these languages, it should be noted that Tibeto-Burman, Austronesian, and Niger-Congo also have voiceless (and aspirated) counterparts. Prenasalisation is considered to be a more archaic form in certain language families, such as Japonic, Kra-Dai, and Tibeto-Burman. Conversely, it is seen to be a relatively recent development in other language groups, including Japonic and Sinitic. Languages

that have prenasalised characteristics are predominantly concentrated in East Asia, Austronesian regions, and Central Africa. These features are the result of internal phonological developments rather than language contact acquisition. Figure 18 illustrates the language groups that possess prenasalisation features, and Figure 19 presents a detailed map of East and Southeast Asia.

Fig. 18 Distribution of the language groups with prenasalised consonants.

Fig. 19 Distribution of the language groups with prenasalised consonants in East and Southeast Asia.

7. Voiceless nasal

The voiceless nasal /ŋ/ is attested in several language families, including Hmong-Mien, Tibeto-Burman, Austroasiatic, Austronesian, and Iranian. Several Saami languages (Uralic), which are not represented on the original LAAA-2 map, also exhibit this feature (Nielsen 1979, Kuruch 1985, Suzuki 2021). The sound is primarily documented in East and Southeast Asia. However, as this is a feature derived from individual sound developments in each language group, it is not considered a regional feature. The Saami languages' case also demonstrates that the given feature is not derived from any regional factors. Figure 20 illustrates the language groups that possess a D/A voiceless nasal, and Figure 21 presents a detailed map of East and Southeast Asia.

Fig. 20 Distribution of the language groups with voiceless nasals.

Fig. 21 Distribution of the language groups with voiceless nasals in East and Southeast Asia.

8. Glottalised stops

Glottalisation can be classified into two categories: preglottalised and postglottalised; however, as both are thought to have originated from disparate description conventions, they are depicted together on the map. The glottalisation feature is attested in several language families, including Ryukyuan of Japonic, Sinitic, Kra-Dai, Hmong-Mien, and Indo-Aryan. These sounds are primarily distributed across East and South Asia, with the preglottalised plosive being frequently associated with an implosive (cf. Section 4). Figure 22 illustrates the language groups that possess D/A glottalised stops, and Figure 23 presents a detailed map of East and Southeast Asia.

Fig. 22 Distribution of the language groups with glottalised stops.

Fig. 23 Distribution of the language groups with glottalised stops in East and Southeast Asia.

9. Lack of D/A nasals

A paucity of D/A nasal sounds is observed in a restricted range of Sinitic, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, and Niger-Congo languages. In Sinitic and Kra-Dai, the principal factor contributing to the absence of the /n/ sound is the merger of /n/ into /l/. However, it appears that both Sinitic and Kra-Dai independently evolved the merger of /n/ into /l/

as there is no evidence of mutual language contact influences. This feature is also attested in Tibeto-Burman (Tujia), which can be attributed to Sinitic language contact (Southwestern Mandarin). It is important to note that this merger does not result in the absence of the sound [n] but rather its continued presence in the phonetic realisation (see Zhang and Levis 2021). Figure 24 illustrates the language groups that do not possess D/A nasal phonemes and Figure 25 presents a detailed map of East Asia.

Fig. 24 Distribution of the language groups exhibiting the lack of D/A nasals.

Fig. 25 Distribution of the language groups exhibiting the lack of D/A nasals in East Asia.

10. Conclusion

This article has addressed the 12 dental/denti-alveolar/alveolar stop series features from Chapter XIII Stop series of LAAA-2, with the data that meet the specified conditions from Asia and Africa being presented on individual maps. This article has demonstrated that the synthetic maps produced as part of the LAAA project are a valuable resource for the interpretation of the mutual relationships between language families in specific regions.

Notes for copyrights

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